

**MIDSAYAP MUNICIPAL LIBRARY AND
INFORMATION CENTER (MMLIC): STUDENTS'
AWARENESS, ACCESS, AND USAGE**

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Midsayap Municipal Library and Information Center (MMLIC): Students' Awareness, Access, and Usage

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the usage of the Midsayap Municipal Library and Information Center (MMLIC), specifically, students' awareness and access to information resources and services. A total of 439 students from the 44 barangays in the municipality served as respondents. Descriptive-correlational research was employed through a one-shot survey method utilizing a researcher-made instrument. Of the 439 respondents, most of them were 18 years old (77.9%), more than half were females (59.5%), and almost all were senior high school students (93.6%). The study also revealed that the majority of the students were not aware of the MMLIC resources and services ($\mu=2.37$), and most of them never accessed ($\mu=38$) and never used ($\mu=1.25$) these. Further, the study found that in terms of age and sex, there was no significant difference in their level of awareness, access, and usage of the resources and services. In terms of educational background, a significant difference was found in their level of awareness ($t=6.080$) and access ($t=2.493$) but not in their extent of use ($t=1.131$). Regarding the level of awareness and access, the SHS had the highest mean. Finally, a sizable gap was found between their level of awareness, access, and usage of the information resources and services and their place of residence. It is concluded that the respondents' lack of access to and underutilization of the MMLIC's resources and services is consistent with their low awareness and may be attributed to it. Due to their lack of knowledge, they did not access and utilize the resources and services. However, the municipal library personnel could have this low level of client awareness as their basis for future initiatives, like an information drive or campaign among Midsayapeños.

Keywords: *Librarian, Library Resources, Library Services, Students, LGU Midsayap, Awareness, Access, and Usage*

Introduction

On June 17, 1994, Republic Act No. 7743, also known as "An Act Providing for the Establishment of Congressional, City, and Municipal Libraries and Barangay Reading Centers Throughout the Philippines, Appropriating the Necessary Funds Thereof and for Other Purposes," was proposed in order to encourage information dissemination and the accessibility of educational materials across the nation. This specifically mandated the establishment of a single public library based on the number of people in each barangay and was seen as important to address the need to provide individuals with new knowledge and information. It aimed to guarantee that members of society's most fundamental unit will have easy access to a wide range of information that is essential for their education (Santiago, 1994).

The future of public libraries is promising. They have adapted, evolved, and redefined their services, collections, and roles in a world of perpetual change and challenges. Public libraries and their personnel have enthusiastically embraced the wave of new technologies, needs, and expectations. They have been encouraged to improve library services and to better serve and satisfy the requirements of their communities with dynamic, responsive, and modern

public library services through a continual cycle of experimentation (Nicholson, 2017).

Given that it is a public library, it is customary to anticipate that many people will require its services. Librarians need to understand the resources that are frequently used and the types of customers they are catering to. They can choose what should be given priority to be updated by learning about the kind of people they are servicing and the content they frequently utilize. Improved customer service is ensured by doing this.

On April 27, 1960, the Midsayap Municipal Public Library was built. The first library librarian, Mrs. Francisco Caballero, oversaw the mandate of RA 7743. For almost 54 years now, the Midsayap library has continued to offer services to its clients. It is a division of the Office of the Sangguniang Bayan, and it particularly offers reading and research resources such as books, manuals, periodicals, newspapers, maps, brochures, journals, and more that provide information for studies, dissertations, and other research-related tasks (Marcial, 2017).

According to the study by Rampola et al. (2019), the majority of 150 respondents to the Citizen Satisfaction Index System said that they were not aware of the Midsayap Information and Reading Center. Only two

out of 10 respondents availed of the services. It was also revealed in their study that most of the reasons why they were not availing of the services of public libraries were because they had not gone or had not been in the public library (Hindi pa nakapunta o nakapasok ng Public Library). Nevertheless, despite their low awareness, the respondents were satisfied with the Information and Reading Center at Municipality of Midsayap in terms of their programs based on the result revealing “the program helped” (nakatulong ang programa) and “the Public Library is beautiful and well organized” (maganda at maayos ang Public Library).

Considering the previous study result, the present study was conducted. The researchers deemed that learning about the presence of the Midsayap Municipal Library and Information Center will foster appreciation among clientele and make discoveries to help them find solutions to information needs. This investigation was conducted to help the researchers assess whether Midsayapeños are currently utilizing the library offerings. Further, this study might attest to the value of municipal public libraries and other interstices of services and resources. For these reasons, the researchers were motivated to pursue the present study to determine the awareness, access, and usage of information resources and services of the Midsayap Municipal Library and Information Center.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the users in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. educational background;
 - 1.4. Residence?
2. What is the users’ level of awareness of the information resources and services of the Midsayap MLC?
3. What is the users’ level of access to the information resources and services of the Midsayap MLC?
4. What is the users’ level of usage of the information resources and services of the Midsayap MLC?
5. Is there a significant difference in the:
 - 5.1. respondents’ level of awareness of the information resources and services of the MMLIC when they are grouped according to their demographic profile.
 - 5.2. respondents’ level of access to the information resources and services of the MMLIC when they are grouped according to their demographic profile.
 - 5.3. respondents’ level of usage of the information resources and services of the MMLIC when they are grouped according to their demographic profile.

6. Is there a significant relationship between:

- 6.1. respondents’ level of awareness and their level of access to the information resources and services of the MMLIC;
- 6.2. respondents’ level of awareness and their level of usage of the information resources and services of the MMLIC;
- 6.3. respondents’ level of access and their level of usage of the information resources and services of the MMLIC

Literature Review

Awareness of Information Resources and Services

In the study by Hussaini et al. (2018), they defined awareness as being aware of something’s existence or having knowledge of a topic at hand based on information. It can also be understood as situational awareness, consciousness, education, success, comprehension, and perception. Academic library statistics, compiled daily by library employees, typically show how much library resources are used in academic libraries. Since use is required to create the library collection, access is the only criterion to decide why a document is kept in the collection.

Public libraries are aware of their responsibility to meet the information demands of all societal segments. In the U.S., the state and federal governments have taken steps to make public libraries a significant source of knowledge for persons in formal occupations. For the growth of libraries and information centers to equip public libraries with information, the National Mission of Libraries, established by the Ministry of Culture, has offered proposals. The public library is thought of being a place for the people. It is a locally accessible portal to knowledge that offers the fundamental building blocks for lifelong learning and promotes the cultural growth of individual and social groups. The public library offers services to all regardless of age, sex, caste, religion, education level, or social studies background. All users generally find library materials pertinent to their wants and requirements (Chellappandi et al., 2021).

The study by Hajek et al. (2019) demonstrates how the age, level of education, and socioeconomic status of the adults surveyed affect the value of children's library services. Additionally, their level of happiness with library services is a crucial factor, suggesting that public libraries can impact how valuable children's library services are.

Libraries are among the essential local institutions for adult and young readership growth. They participate in formal and informal programs that assist education, employment, careers, business, and cultural activities while offering a wide range of information services to a variety of groups (Efe, 2021). Public libraries are undoubtedly important, particularly in promoting mass literacy and educating people about the country and its administration (Chauhan & Kumbar, 2019). Libraries play a crucial role in promoting education, training, research, and other development activities by giving social science researchers broader and deeper access to information (Kemparaju, 2019). The degree to which the Librarian carries out the various actions will impact the amount of awareness, availability, and accessibility of library resources (Ibeun, 2017).

Access to Information Resources and Services

Users of the library come to the library to get enough current information in printed and non-printed formats for efficient learning and research that satisfies their information needs and enables them to address significant problems. They can get this information from library resources and services, which also include fresh concepts, information, and data from academic and applied research (Arce, 2020). It is important to spread information about the services, which will lead to a high level of awareness and, more importantly, a good level of perception of the breadth of services offered by the library. The library should take advantage of the chance to publish newsletters, brochures, booklets, and journals to increase accessibility. Themes on the purpose of libraries, how to use their resources, and briefs on new advances aimed at enhancing their offerings may be included (Alian, 2012).

The study of Mubofu and Malekani (2021) discovered issues that prevented the effective use of library resources and services, including high data costs, information overload, insufficient skills to evaluate information sources, password and login frustrations, a lack of thorough online tutorials from OUT library, a lack of information search skills, a lack of distance librarians assigned to support remote students, a lack of accessible, full-text resources, a lack of educational resources, and a lack of university-level resources. The Special Collection, followed by the Librarian's services and the general collection, is the resource to which most respondents have the most access. The bulk of library services was heavily used by the responders, who were students and faculty. They have been able to use the library's circulation loan services, discussion room, reference section, and reader service

section, most of all of them (Thaug, 2016).

Usage of Information Resources and Services

The library's role is to provide information to users so they can efficiently and effectively meet their needs. It keeps the efficiency of the services, encouraging users to establish lifetime reading and research habits utilizing the library and the technology it provides. Completing the client's educational and research requirements is of utmost importance. One of the things that encourage people to accept the skills, knowledge, and ideas they contain is the library (Orlopa & Rabaca, 2015).

Users are unaware of the sources of bibliographic information they are seeking. Factors like accessibility and awareness fuel the effective use of library resources. Over the years, the need to make access easier has not received the attention it needs, which has led to low utilization of the catalog and the inaccessibility of the resources by students. The materials and services offered by libraries will be significantly impacted, either directly or indirectly (Atanda & Ugwulebo, 2017).

Successful library operations are determined by staff competency, collection balance, and upgrades. Fortunately, in the Philippines, the Leyte Normal University (LNU) administration regularly updates the university's library materials so that both graduate and undergraduate students can use them (Alcober, 2022). The university library has an excellent collection and offers excellent information services. It has been discovered that most library patrons are pleased with the University library's operating hours, physical facilities, information resources, and services. Most library patrons give positive feedback regarding the hours, spaces, and library information sources. Meanwhile, in India, the K L University Library should run more user education programs for its patrons and offer training sessions for using electronic databases (Kona et al., 2016).

A study by Eyiolorunshe and Eluwole (2017) found that there were no specific difficulties in using the library's resources. A significant portion of respondents, according to the survey, disagreed that "library workers are not willing to give services or help." Public information centers should be created to fulfill both current requirements and future expectations. Specialists in public libraries must have technical and professional training. Information is, therefore, an essential part of all human endeavors and daily life in all civilizations. Information has

transformed into a product that is packaged and sold for a reasonable price. It is an essential resource that must be developed to achieve organizational goals and management decisions related to a survival strategy.

Ikenwe and Adegbilero-Iwari (2014) showed that most of the study's participants who used public libraries did so at least once a week. In order to retain current and potential users, public libraries in the twenty-first century must urgently improve the level of services they provide. This contradicts several research pieces claiming that people do not visit public libraries. Since people no longer view public libraries as a fungus, it should be recognized from this study that usage has improved so far in this century.

Methodology

This study is a descriptive correlational study that was conducted using a one-shot survey method. Since the study focused on determining the awareness, access, and usage of information resources and services of the MMLIC, the descriptive research method was the most appropriate.

Correlational research was used to identify patterns and connections between variables and to forecast future events using available information. This study determined whether there were relationships between the identified variables.

Participants/Respondents

The study's respondents were 439 students who were 18 years old and above, residents of Midsayap, and enrolled in the schools within the municipality at the time of the study. The respondents were selected through purposive and snowball techniques.

Purposive sampling is when researchers carefully consider how they will create a sample population. The Snowball technique was used by tapping friends and peers of the identified respondents based on the specified criteria.

Instruments of the Study

This study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire to gather data on the awareness, access, and usage of the MMLIC. The questionnaire was divided into four (4) parts which inquired into the following areas: (part 1) respondents' demographic characteristics; (part 2) awareness; (part 3) access; and (part 4) usage. Content validity by experts and pilot testing was conducted in

order to know the questionnaire's reliability.

The reliability test was performed on the questionnaire to determine whether the items were internally consistent. According to David (2005, as cited in Limos, 2019), the consistency of the responses or scores received by the respondents to the various questionnaire items is referred to as reliability. The reliability attribute of the test is formed by the ideas of consistency and accuracy. Ten college students were chosen at random to receive it, and the responses' reliability was statistically assessed. Acero (2006, as cited in Limos, 2019) states that the research instrument is reliable if the reliability value is high, 0.071 to 0.090, or extremely high, 0.91 to 0.99.

The reliability of the questionnaire was solved using SPSS 25. All the 10 cases indicated the validity and reliability statistics for the three variables as 0.977 for awareness, 0.983 for access, and 0.987 for usage. According to Nunally (1967, as cited in Chang & Fisher, 2003), an alpha reliability estimate of 0.60 or greater is acceptable. Therefore, the figures indicated that they were satisfactory regarding their internal consistency.

Procedure

The researchers sent a letter to the Municipal Mayor of Midsayap requesting permission to survey selected Midsayap barangays as part of the study. Upon approval, the researchers met with the municipal librarians to inform them about the commencement of data collection from the respondents. They sent a letter to all barangays and schools requesting their consent to allow us to survey their students. Every school's principal in Midsayap gave us permission to conduct the survey. There are still 50 forms, including invalid ones. Given that just 439 people were in our target demographic, they did not include many superfluous forms in our data. The data to be gathered would be confidentially and exclusively used for this study only. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. With the presence of advisers, the researcher first explained the parts and mechanics of answering to the respondents and personally administered the questionnaire during the set date.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data that the researchers have gathered. The data are shown in tabular form with their corresponding interpretations and analyses.

Profile of the Respondents

Age

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of age. It shows that 342 (79.9.0%) of them were 18 years old, 52 (11.8%), and 45 (10.3%) were 20 years old and above. This means that most of the students were 18 years old

Table 1. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of age*

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 years old	342	77.9
19 years old	52	11.8
20 years old and above	45	10.3
Total	439	100

Sex

Presented in the second table are the frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. As can be seen, more than half of them were females (261 or 59.5%), while the rest (178 or 40.5%) were males. This means that the present study's respondents were female-dominated.

Table 2. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	178	40.5
Female	261	59.5
Total	439	100

Educational Background

Table 3 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of their educational background. Data revealed that the majority of the respondents were in senior high school (411 or 93.6%) compared to their junior high school (28 or 6.4%) counterparts.

Table 3. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of their educational background.*

Educational Background	Frequency	Percent
Junior High School	28	6.4
Senior High School	411	93.6
Total	439	100

Residence

The frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of their residence are presented in Table 4. It shows that ten students from each of the 43 barangays and nine students in one barangay served as respondents to the study. Overall, there were 439 respondents.

Table 4. *Frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents in terms of their residence*

<i>Residence</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Poblacion 1	10	2.3
Poblacion 2	10	2.3
Poblacion 3	10	2.3
Poblacion 4	10	2.3
Poblacion 5	10	2.3
Poblacion 6	10	2.3
Poblacion 7	10	2.3
Poblacion 8	10	2.3
Agriculture	10	2.3
Anonang	10	2.3
Arizona	10	2.3
Bagumba	10	2.3
Baliki	10	2.3
Bitoka	10	2.3
Bual Norte	10	2.3
Bual Sur	10	2.3
Bulanan Upper	10	2.3
Central	10	2.3
Bulanan		
Central Glad	10	2.3
Central	10	2.3
Katingawan		
Ilbocean	10	2.3
Kimagango	10	2.3
Kiwanan	10	2.3
Lagumbingan	10	2.3
Lower Glad	10	2.3
Lower	10	2.3
Katingawan		
Malamote	10	2.3
Milaya	10	2.3
Nalin	10	2.3
Nes	10	2.3
Polongoguen	10	2.3
Patindeguen	10	2.3
Rangaban	10	2.3
Sadaan	10	2.3
Salunayan	10	2.3
San Isidro	10	2.3
San Pedro	10	2.3
<i>Residence</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Santa Cruz	10	2.3
Upper Glad 1	10	2.3
Upper Glad 2	10	2.3
Upper labas	10	2.3
Villarica	10	2.3
Macasendeg	10	2.3
Lomopog	9	2.1
Total	439	100

Users' Level of Awareness of the Information Resources and Services of the MMLIC

Table 5 shows the mean and interpretation of the users' level of awareness of the information resources and services of the MMLIC. The table specifically shows that the awareness of library resources in the reserve section, which contains history books, yielded a mean of 2.78. Awareness about journals (newspaper, magazine) had a mean of 2.71; the reference section, which contains encyclopedias, dictionaries, thesauri, and atlases, had a mean of 2.59; and the reserve section, which contains copies of the Bible, had a mean of 2.57. Further, respondents' awareness of the handbook had a mean of 2.56; the children's section, which contains storybooks for kids, had a mean of 2.55. Finally, educational charts had a mean of 2.54. The finding implies that out of 26 resources, people are only aware of seven library resources. The students are not aware of other resources offered by the municipal library.

Table 5. Mean and interpretation of the users' level of awareness of the information resources and services of the MMLIC

Items	Mean	V.D.	Interpretation
RESOURCES			
I am aware that the Midsayap MLIC has ...			
<i>Reference Section</i>			
Encyclopedias, dictionaries, thesauri, Atlases	2.59	Agree	Aware
Handbook	2.56	Agree	Aware
Guinness book of Records	2.38	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>Circulation Section</i>			
Journals (newspaper, magazine)	2.71	Agree	Aware
Filipiniana books	2.50	Disagree	Not Aware
Fiction books	2.50	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>Reserve Section</i>			
History books	2.78	Agree	Aware
Copies of the Bible	2.57	Agree	Aware
Rizal Collection	2.38	Disagree	Not Aware
Official Gazette	2.29	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>Special Collection</i>			
Trophies, certificates, awards	2.50	Disagree	Not Aware
CD-ROM	2.03	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>Children's Section</i>			
Storybooks for kids	2.55	Agree	Aware
Educational Chart	2.54	Agree	Aware
Encyclopedia for kids	2.36	Disagree	Not Aware
Toys	2.22	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>Youth Development Section</i>			
SK Accomplishment Reports	2.31	Disagree	Not Aware
DILG memoranda	2.13	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>Local History Section (1945-1965)</i>			
Barangay Histories	2.37	Disagree	Not Aware
Ordinances	2.28	Disagree	Not Aware
Resolutions	2.27	Disagree	Not Aware
Souvenir Programs	2.25	Disagree	Not Aware
SOMA (State of Municipal Address)	2.25	Disagree	Not Aware
Minutes	2.20	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>GAD Section</i>			
Training Manual	2.29	Disagree	Not Aware
Table 5 continued			
Magna Carta for Women	2.22	Disagree	Not Aware
<i>Services</i>			
I am aware that the Midsayap MLIC offers...			
Borrowing of books/materials	2.37	Disagree	Not Aware
Photocopying	2.28	Disagree	Not Aware
Reference services	2.21	Disagree	Not Aware
Grand Mean	2.37	Disagree	Not Aware

In terms of awareness of the library services of the MMLIC, as shown in the table, the borrowing of books/materials gained a mean of 2.37; photocopying had a mean of 2.28, and the reference services had a mean of 2.21. These figures indicate that the students were less aware of the said services. The data revealed a grand mean of 2.37, meaning that the students of Midsayap were less aware of the information resources and services offered by the MMLIC. The result implies that the center rarely did or never did a library promotional activity that could inform clientele about its resources and services.

The result conforms to the study of Rampola et al. (2019), which revealed that most respondents were unaware of the MMLIC. Only two out of 10 respondents availed of the services. Most of the reasons why people did not avail of the services of public libraries could be attributed to low awareness about its resources and services.

Users' Level of Access to the Information Resources and Services of the MMLIC

The mean and interpretation of the users' level of access to information resources and services of the MMLIC are reflected in Table 6. Data reveal that the highest mean of accessed information resources was for journals (1.58), which belongs to the circulation section, and the lowest mean of accessed information resources was for the Guinness Book of Records (1.25) in the reference section. In addition, the result describes that the 439 respondents were not aware that there were available resources in MMLIC, so they were not able to access the resources. Further, data on the level of access to the municipal library's services, such as borrowing books or materials, yielded a low mean of 1.43; photocopying had a mean of 1.45, and reference services had a mean of 1.36. The grand mean of 1.38 indicated that the students of Midsayap never accessed information resources and services offered by the MMLIC.

Table 6. Mean and interpretation of the users' level of access to the information resources and services of the MMLIC

Items	Mean	V.D.	Interpretation
RESOURCES			
I can access it from the Midsayap MLIC...			
<i>Reference Section</i>			
Encyclopedias, dictionaries, thesauri, Atlases	1.35	Never	Never Accessed
Handbook	1.33	Never	Never Accessed
Guinness book of Records	1.25	Never	Never Accessed
<i>Circulation Section</i>			
Filipiniana books	1.28	Never	Never Accessed
Journals (newspaper, magazine)	1.58	Never	Never Accessed
Fiction books	1.45	Never	Never Accessed
<i>Reserve Section</i>			
History books	1.53	Never	Never Accessed
Official Gazette	1.32	Never	Never Accessed
Rizal Collection	1.36	Never	Never Accessed
Copies of the Bible	1.43	Never	Never Accessed
<i>Special Collection</i>			
Trophies, certificates, awards	1.40	Never	Never Accessed
CD-ROM	1.30	Never	Never Accessed
<i>Children's Section</i>			
Toys	1.41	Never	Never Accessed
Encyclopedia for kids	1.42	Never	Never Accessed
Storybooks for kids	1.44	Never	Never Accessed
Educational Chart	1.43	Never	Never Accessed
<i>Youth Development Section</i>			
SK Accomplishment Reports	1.37	Never	Never Accessed
DILG memoranda	1.33	Never	Never Accessed
<i>Local History Section (1945-1965)</i>			
Ordinances	1.36	Never	Never Accessed
Resolutions	1.33	Never	Never Accessed
Minutes	1.33	Never	Never Accessed
Souvenir Programs	1.38	Never	Never Accessed
SOMA (State of Municipal Address)	1.37	Never	Never Accessed
Barangay Histories	1.37	Never	Never Accessed
<i>GAD Section</i>			
Magna Carta for Women	1.31	Never	Never Accessed
Training Manual	1.35	Never	Never Accessed
SERVICES			
Borrowing of books/materials	1.43	Never	Never Accessed
Photocopying	1.45	Never	Never Accessed
Reference services	1.36	Never	Never Accessed
Grand Mean	1.38	Never	Never Accessed

Nevertheless, information resource access data still showed a favorable implication. This means that the students of Midsayap will be able to access the municipal library's resources and services anytime with the proper awareness program, information drive, or information dissemination. This implies that Midsayapeños did not access the public library because of low awareness.

Users' Level of Usage of Information Resources and Services of the MMLIC

Table 7 shows the mean and interpretation of the users' level of usage of information resources and services of the MMLIC. As can be gleaned, in terms of library resources and services, all items were rated "never used." It means that the students of Midsayap were not using the library resources and services. Among the resources in the center, history books got the highest mean of 1.35. The result indicates that if the students were unaware of the resources and services, they would not be able to access them, and if they could not, they would not be able to use the services provided in the library. This implies that library information resources and services are never utilized since the students' of Midsayap never accessed the Midsayap Municipal Library and Information Center.

Table 7. Mean and interpretation of the users' level of usage of the information resources and services of the MMLIC

Items	Mean	V.D.	Interpretation
RESOURCES			
In the Midsayap MMLIC, I can use...			
<i>Reference Section</i>			
Encyclopedias, dictionaries, thesauri, Atlases	1.23	Never	Never Used
Handbook	1.29	Never	Never Used
Guinness book of Records	1.23	Never	Never Used
<i>Circulation Section</i>			
Filipiniana books	1.26	Never	Never Used
Journals (newspaper, magazine)	1.33	Never	Never Used
Fiction books	1.28	Never	Never Used
<i>Reserve Section</i>			
History books	1.35	Never	Never Used
Official Gazette	1.24	Never	Never Used
Rizal Collection	1.24	Never	Never Used
Copies of the Bible	1.27	Never	Never Used
<i>Special Collection</i>			
Trophies, certificates, awards	1.27	Never	Never Used
CD-ROM	1.22	Never	Never Used
<i>Children's Section</i>			
Toys	1.30	Never	Never Used
Encyclopedia for kids	1.31	Never	Never Used
Storybooks for kids	1.33	Never	Never Used
Educational Chart	1.27	Never	Never Used
<i>Youth Development Section</i>			
SK Accomplishment Reports	1.23	Never	Never Used
DILG memoranda	1.21	Never	Never Used
<i>Local History Section (1945-1965)</i>			
Ordinances	1.21	Never	Never Used
Resolutions	1.22	Never	Never Used
Minutes	1.21	Never	Never Used
Souvenir Programs	1.20	Never	Never Used
SOMA (State of Municipal Address)	1.21	Never	Never Used
Barangay Histories	1.21	Never	Never Used
<i>GAD Section</i>			
Magna Carta for Women	1.22	Never	Never Used
Training Manual	1.22	Never	Never Used
SERVICES			
Borrowing of books/materials	1.33	Never	Never Used
Photocopying	1.28	Never	Never Used
Reference services	1.23	Never	Never Used
Grand Mean	1.25	Never	Never Used

Table 8 shows the One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) between the respondents' profile and their awareness, access, and usage of information resources and services of the Midsayap Municipal Library and Information Center (MMLIC).

Table 8. *One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) between the respondents' profile and their awareness, access, and usage of the information resources and services of the Midsayap MLIC.*

Variables			F	p (2-tailed)	Decision	
Age	Awareness		1.530	0.155	Accept H ₀₁	
	Access		1.041	0.401	Accept H ₀₂	
	Usage		1.410	0.149	Accept H ₀₃	
Residence	Awareness	Arizona	1.01 ^a	3.953**	0.000	Reject H ₁₀
		Central Glad	3.09 ^b			
		Ilbocean	3.15 ^b			
	Access	Poblacion 6	1.09 ^a	2.116**	0.000	Reject H ₁₁
		Arizona	1.00 ^a			
		Central Glad	2.21 ^b			
		Santa Cruz	1.09 ^a			
		Upper Labas	1.01 ^a			
	Usage	Poblacion 6	1.00 ^a	2.038**	0.000	Reject H ₁₂
		Arizona	1.00 ^a			
		Bitoka	1.02 ^a			
		Bulanan	1.02 ^a			
		Upper				
		per				
		Milaya	1.01 ^a			
Santa Cruz	1.01 ^a					
Upper Labas	1.00 ^a					
Macasendeg	1.00 ^a					
Lomopog	2.00 ^b					

As presented in Table 8, the computed F -values between the respondent's age and their level of awareness, access, and usage are 1.530, 1.041, and 1.410, respectively. They are not significant since their p -values are higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypotheses (H_{01} , H_{02} , H_{03}) were accepted. This means that there was no significant difference in the respondent's level of awareness, access, and usage of information resources and services of the MMLIC when they were grouped according to their age. The results imply that the Midsayapeños, regardless of their age, have the same level of awareness, access, and usage of the center.

The table also shows that the computed F -value between the respondent's residence and their level of awareness is 3.953, and it is significant since its p -value is lower than the 0.01 level of significance. Hence, H_{10} was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference in the respondent's level of awareness of information resources and services of the MMLIC when they were grouped according to their residence. Their level of awareness could be attributed to the proximity of their residence to the municipal library. When post hoc tests were performed, there was a significant difference ($\alpha=0.05$) between the level of awareness of respondents who reside in Arizona ($\bar{x}=1.01$) and respondents who reside in Central Glad ($\bar{x}=3.09$) and Ilbocean ($\bar{x}=3.15$).

Subsequently, between the respondent's residence and their level of access, the F -value is 2.116, which is significant since its p -value is lower than the 0.01 level of significance. Hence, H_{11} was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference in the respondent's level of access to information resources

and services of the MMLIC when they were grouped according to their residence. The result implies that if they are not aware that there is a municipal library, they will not be able to access it. When post hoc tests were performed, there was a significant difference ($\alpha=0.05$) between the level of access of respondents who reside in Poblacion 6 ($\bar{x}=1.09$) Arizona ($\bar{x}=1.00$) Santa Cruz ($\bar{x}=1.09$) and Upper Labas ($\bar{x}=1.01$) and respondents who reside in Central Glad ($\bar{x}=2.21$).

Furthermore, between the respondent's residence and their usage level, the F -value is 2.038, which is significant since its p -value is lower than the 0.01 level of significance. Hence, H_{12} was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference in the respondent's level of usage of information resources and services of the MMLIC when they were grouped according to their residence. The result revealed that if they were not aware of and had access to the resources and services offered at MMLIC, they would not use the items there. When post hoc tests were performed, there was a significant difference between the level of usage of respondents who reside in Poblacion 6, Arizona, Upper Labas, Macasendeg ($\bar{x}=1.00$) Bitoka, Bulanan Upper ($\bar{x}=1.02$) and Milaya, Santa Cruz ($\bar{x}=1.01$) and respondents who reside in Lomopog ($\bar{x}=2.00$).

Table 9 shows the computed t -values between the respondent's sex and education and their level of awareness, access, and usage. The table also shows that when the respondents are grouped according to their sex, the t -values are 0.485, 0.069, and 0.087 for awareness, access, and usage, respectively, and they are not significant since their p -values are higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypotheses (H_{04} , H_{05} , H_{06}) were accepted. This means that there was no significant difference in the respondent's level of awareness, access, and usage of information resources and services of the MMLIC when they were grouped according to their sex. Furthermore, this means that regardless of their sex, their level of awareness, access, and usage of the MMLIC is the same.

Table 9. *The t-test computation between the respondents' sex and education and their awareness, access, and usage of information resources and services of the Midsayap MLLIC*

Variables	Mean	t	p (2-tailed)	Decision	
Sex	Awareness	0.485	0.628	Accept H ₀₄	
	Access	0.069	0.945	Accept H ₀₅	
	Usage	0.087	0.931	Accept H ₀₆	
Education	Awareness	JHS 1.41	6.080**	0.000	Reject H ₀₇
		SHS 2.40			
	Access	JHS 1.14	2.493*	0.013	Reject H ₀₈
		SHS 1.46			
	Usage	1.131	0.259	Accept H ₀₉	

When grouped educational background, there was a significant difference in the level of awareness of information resources and services of the MMLIC. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀₇) was rejected. JHS yielded $\bar{x}=1.41$ and SHS $\bar{x}=2.40$, $t=6.080$, $p=0.000$. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀₇) was rejected. The result could be attributed to the senior high school student's high exposure to the library compared to the junior high school. Furthermore, there was a significant difference in the level of access to information resources and services to the MMLIC when they were grouped according to their educational background. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀₈) was rejected. JHS yielded $\bar{x}=1.14$ and SHS $\bar{x}=1.46$, $t=2.493$, $p=0.013$. This connects that the higher awareness of senior high school could be attributed to their number of years in education.

Nevertheless, there was no significant difference in the level of usage of information resources and services of the MMLIC when they were grouped according to their educational background. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀₉) was accepted. For H₀₉, $t=2.493$, $p=0.01$. This implies that the educational background of the students has no significant difference in the level of usage. Regardless of their educational backgrounds, all respondents tended not to use the library.

In identifying the existing relationship among the respondents' awareness, access, and usage of the information resources and services provided by the MMLIC, Pearson's Product-Moment Coefficient of Correlation (Pearson's r) was used.

Table 10 shows a relationship among the aforementioned variables, which is significant at a 1% significance level. The level of awareness and level of access to the information resources and services of the

MMLIC led to the decision to reject H₁₃, which means that there is a positive moderate linear relationship between the respondent's level of awareness and level of access ($r=0.442$). The results suggest that the higher the level of awareness, the higher is level of access. Additionally, hypothesis H₁₂ was rejected, which means that there is a significant relationship based on the qualitative interpretation of ($r=0.802$). The result shows that there is a positive, strong linear relationship between the respondent's level of access and level of usage. The higher the level of access, the higher is level of usage. Besides, the hypothesis (H₁₃) was rejected, which means that there is a significant relationship based on the qualitative interpretation of r (0.295). The result specifies that there is a positive weak linear relationship between the respondent's level of usage and level of awareness. The higher the level of usage, the higher is level of awareness.

Table 10. *Correlations among the respondents' awareness, access, and usage of information resources and services of the MMLIC*

Variables	Awareness	Access	Usage	Sig.	Interpretation	Decision
Awareness		0.442**		0.000	Moderate Linear Relationship	Reject H ₀₁₃
Access			0.802**	0.000	Strong Linear Relationship	Reject H ₀₁₅
Usage	0.295*			0.000	Weak Linear Relationship	Reject H ₀₁₄

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it is concluded that the low awareness of the respondents can be attributed to their non-access and non-use of the resources and services of the MMLIC.

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